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Social Skills and Peer Relationship Quality among Secondary School Students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the extent to which social skills predict peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of 6,767 senior secondary two students in public secondary schools, from which a sample of 645 students was selected using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Social Skills and Peer Relationship Quality Questionnaire (SSPRQQ). The instrument was face validated by experts, and its reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding an overall coefficient of 0.81. Data were analyzed using simple linear regression statistics. Findings revealed that interpersonal skills ($R = 0.677$; $R^2 = 0.458$) and empathy ($R = 0.698$; $R^2 = 0.487$) predict peer relationship quality to a moderate extent, while social awareness ($R = 0.859$; $R^2 = 0.737$) predicts peer relationship

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quality to a high extent. The hypotheses tested showed that interpersonal skills ($F = 204.43, p < 0.05$), empathy ($F = 108.17, p < 0.05$), and social awareness ($F = 212.11, p < 0.05$) significantly predict peer relationship quality. The study concluded that social skills are significant determinants of peer relationship quality among secondary school students, with social awareness being the strongest predictor. It was recommended among others that secondary school authorities in Uyo Local Government Area should incorporate social skills training programs into the school system to enhance students' interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness. The findings have important implications for counseling, particularly in designing interventions to improve students' social competence and interpersonal relationships.

Keywords: social skills, interpersonal skills, empathy, social awareness, peer relationships, quality

Introduction

Within the school environment, students are expected to relate effectively with peers, teachers, and other members of the school community. These interactions can shape their social experiences and determine the quality of relationships they build. When students maintain high-quality peer relationships, they may experience social acceptance, emotional support, and a sense of belonging. Such relationships also promote cooperation, enhance classroom participation, and contribute to students' social competence and emotional stability. On the other hand, poor peer relationship quality may result in isolation, conflict, bullying, and negative social experiences, which can hinder students' overall development. Students who experience poor peer relationships may also develop feelings of rejection, low self-esteem, and difficulty adjusting to the school environment (Adeyemi, 2020). Peer relationship quality refers to the degree of trust, support, cooperation, and positive interaction that exists among students in their relationships with one another, as stated by Nlebem (2020). In addition, Douglas and Hillary (2021) described peer relationship quality as the extent to which students experience mutual respect,

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acceptance, and emotional connection in their interactions with classmates, while Ayoola (2022) viewed it as the level of positive engagement and supportive communication that exists within peer groups.

However, the quality of peer relationships among students may largely depend on the level of social skills they possess in interacting with others. According to Silas (2022), social skills refer to the abilities that enable individuals to communicate effectively, understand others, and behave appropriately in social contexts. Students who possess strong social skills are more likely to interact positively with peers, resolve conflicts amicably, and sustain supportive friendships. Conversely, students with poor social skills may experience difficulties in relating with others, leading to strained or unhealthy peer relationships. Social skills of interest in this study include interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness.

Interpersonal skills refer to the ability of individuals to interact effectively with others through communication, cooperation, and relationship-building behaviors (Obi & Nweke, 2023). Students with strong interpersonal skills may be able to initiate conversations, maintain friendships, and collaborate with peers in academic and social activities. These skills promote mutual understanding and respect, thereby enhancing the quality of peer relationships. On the other hand, poor interpersonal skills may lead to misunderstandings, conflicts, and social withdrawal, which can negatively affect students' relationships with peers.

As highlighted by Oraye (2022), empathy refers to the ability of individuals to understand and share the feelings of others, thereby demonstrating care, concern, and emotional sensitivity. Students who exhibit empathy are more likely to support their peers during difficult times, avoid hurtful behaviors, and maintain harmonious relationships. Empathy fosters trust and emotional connection among students, which are essential for building strong peer relationships. In contrast, lack of empathy may result in insensitivity, aggression, and poor social interactions, which can weaken the quality of peer relationships.

Social awareness refers to the ability of individuals to recognize social cues, understand group dynamics, and behave appropriately in different social situations (Ukaegbu & Obikoya, 2017). Students who are socially aware are better able to interpret the emotions and behaviors of others, adjust their responses accordingly,

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and maintain positive interactions. This ability can enhance their acceptance among peers and contributes to the development of healthy relationships. Conversely, students who lack social awareness may misinterpret social situations, leading to inappropriate behavior and strained peer relationships.

From the foregoing, understanding how social skills predict the peer relationship quality of students is essential for promoting healthy social interactions and positive school experiences among adolescents. Effective social skills can help students build supportive friendships, resolve conflicts, and maintain harmonious relationships. It is against this background that this study sought to investigate the extent to which social skills predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

The quality of peer relationships among secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State has become a growing concern, as it influences students' social experiences, emotional well-being, and overall development. In recent times, there have been increasing observations of conflicts, bullying, social isolation, and unhealthy peer interactions among students. These issues suggest possible deficiencies in students' ability to interact effectively and maintain positive relationships with their peers.

Despite the importance of social skills in enhancing peer relationship quality, there is limited empirical evidence on how specific dimensions of social skills such as interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness predict the quality of peer relationships among secondary school students. While several studies have focused on academic achievement and behavioral outcomes, less attention has been given to the role of social skills in shaping peer relationship quality, particularly within the context of secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. This creates a gap in knowledge that needs to be addressed. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate the extent to which social skills predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

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Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be beneficial to students, teachers, school counselors, parents, curriculum planners, and researchers. To students, it will help them understand the importance of social skills such as interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness in building and maintaining positive peer relationships. It will also enable students to develop appropriate social behaviors that can enhance cooperation, reduce conflicts, and improve their overall social experiences within the school environment.

More so, teachers will benefit from the findings of this study, as it will provide them with insights into how students' social skills influence the quality of their peer relationships. This knowledge will help teachers to adopt effective classroom management strategies, promote positive interactions among students, and create a supportive learning environment that encourages teamwork and mutual respect.

The outcome of the study will be useful to school counselors as it will provide empirical information that can guide counseling interventions aimed at improving students' social skills and peer relationships. Counselors will be better equipped to design programs and strategies that enhance interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness among students, thereby reducing cases of conflict, bullying, and social isolation.

Additionally, parents will benefit from the findings of this study, as it will help them understand the role of social skills in shaping their children's peer relationships. This awareness will encourage parents to support the development of positive social behaviors at home, thereby complementing efforts made by the school in promoting healthy social interactions among students.

Furthermore, the findings of this study will also be beneficial to curriculum planners and educational policymakers, as they will provide useful information for the development of programs and policies that promote social skill development in schools. This may lead to the inclusion of social and emotional learning components in the school curriculum to enhance students' interpersonal competence and social adjustment.

Finally, the study will serve as valuable reference material for future researchers by contributing to existing literature on social skills and peer relationship quality. It will also provide a basis for further studies in related areas, particularly within the context of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom State and beyond.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which social skills predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

- i. The extent to which interpersonal skills predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students.
- ii. The extent to which empathy predicts the peer relationship quality among secondary school students.
- iii. The extent to which social awareness predicts the peer relationship quality among secondary school students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. To what extent do interpersonal skills predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students?
- ii. To what extent does empathy predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students?
- iii. To what extent does social awareness predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

- i. Interpersonal skills do not significantly predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students.

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- ii. Empathy does not significantly predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students.
- iii. Social awareness does not significantly predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on the extent to which social skills predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Social skills variables such as interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness served as the independent variables, while peer relationship quality was the dependent variable. The study was delimited to senior secondary two students in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area during the 2025/2026 academic session.

Theoretical Framework

Social Intelligence Theory by Edward Thorndike (1920)

Social Intelligence Theory was propounded by Edward Thorndike in 1920. It focuses on the ability of individuals to understand and manage people, as well as to act wisely in human relations. The theory emphasizes that social intelligence is a key component of effective social functioning, enabling individuals to interact appropriately, interpret social cues, and maintain meaningful relationships. According to Thorndike, individuals who possess high social intelligence are better able to navigate social situations, communicate effectively, and respond appropriately to the emotions and behaviors of others.

Social Intelligence Theory further explains that social competence involves a combination of skills such as interpersonal interaction, empathy, and social awareness. These skills enable individuals to build rapport, resolve conflicts, and maintain harmonious relationships. In the context of adolescents, social intelligence develops through continuous interaction with peers, teachers, and the broader social environment. Students who possess strong social skills are more likely to demonstrate positive behaviors such as cooperation, respect, and effective communication, which are essential for successful social interactions.

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The relevance of Social Intelligence Theory to this study lies in its explanation of how social skills influence interpersonal relationships among students. Secondary school students who exhibit interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness are better equipped to understand their peers, communicate effectively, and respond appropriately in social situations. These abilities enhance their capacity to build and maintain positive peer relationships. Therefore, Social Intelligence Theory provides a useful framework for understanding how social skills predict the peer relationship quality of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Sociometric Theory by Jacob L. Moreno (1934)

Jacob L. Moreno propounded Sociometric Theory in 1934. The theory focuses on the measurement and analysis of social relationships within groups. The theory emphasizes that individuals' positions within social groups are determined by patterns of attraction, acceptance, and rejection among members. According to Moreno, peer relationships can be understood through sociometric status, which reflects the degree to which an individual is liked, accepted, or rejected by others within a group.

Sociometric theory explains that individuals who are accepted by their peers tend to experience positive social interactions, higher self-esteem, and a sense of belonging, while those who are rejected or neglected may experience isolation, conflict, and poor social outcomes. The theory also highlights that the quality of peer relationships is influenced by individuals' behaviors, communication patterns, and social competencies. Students who display positive social behaviors are more likely to be accepted and form strong peer connections, whereas those with poor social behaviors may struggle to build and maintain relationships.

The relevance of sociometric theory to this study is evident in its explanation of how peer relationships are formed and maintained within the school environment. Secondary school students who possess strong social skills such as interpersonal competence, empathy, and social awareness are more likely to be accepted by their peers and develop high-quality relationships. On the other hand, students who lack these skills may experience rejection or difficulty in forming meaningful connections. Therefore, sociometric theory provides a useful

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framework for understanding how social skills influence peer relationship quality among secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between social skills and peer relationship quality of secondary school students. According to Nworgu (2015), correlational research design is used to establish relationships among variables as they naturally occur. This design is therefore suitable for investigating how social skills (interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness) predict the peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 6,767 SS Two students in public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. At the time of this study, there were 15 public secondary schools in the area of the study (Akwa Ibom State Secondary Schools Board, 2026).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study consisted of 645 SS Two students drawn from a population of 6,767 SS Two students in public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample size was derived using Taro Yamane's formula for a finite population. A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the respondents. The population was first stratified based on schools within the local government area, after which the sample was proportionately distributed according to the size of each stratum. Thereafter, a simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents from the respective schools.

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Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire titled “Social Skills and Peer Relationship Quality Questionnaire (SSPRQQ)” developed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, namely Section A and Section B. Section A consisted of 18 items designed to measure the independent sub-variables of social skills (interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness), while Section B consisted of 15 items that measured respondents’ peer relationship quality. The items were structured on a four-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, comprising two experts in guidance and counseling and one expert in measurement and evaluation, all from the Faculty of Education. The experts examined the instrument for clarity, relevance, appropriateness of language, and adequacy in measuring the variables under study. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the instrument to ensure that it adequately measured the social skills and peer relationship quality of secondary school students.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established using the internal consistency method. The instrument was administered to 30 SS Two students who were part of the population but were not selected for the study. The data obtained were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability coefficients obtained were 0.80 for interpersonal skills, 0.83 for empathy, 0.78 for social awareness, and 0.82 for peer relationship quality, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.81. These values indicated that the instrument was reliable for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher used a direct administration method in collecting data for the study. Permission was obtained from the school authorities before administering the questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents in

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their respective schools. The purpose of the study was explained to the students, and they were assured of confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. The respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, after which the completed copies were collected immediately to ensure a high return rate.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using simple linear regression statistics. The R values of simple linear regression statistics were used to answer all the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested using the F-ratio associated with the simple linear regression coefficient at the 0.05 alpha level of significance. All data were subjected to analysis using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Decision Rule

The following decision rule guided the answering of all the research questions:

- 0.80 - 1.00 Very high extent
- 0.60 - 0.799 High extent
- 0.40 - 0.599 Moderate extent
- 0.20 - 0.399 Low extent
- 0.00 - 0.199 Very low extent

More so, if the value of significant value is less than the .05 alpha level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significance was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was upheld and vice versa.

Results

Table 1: Simple Regression Coefficient on the Extent to Which Interpersonal Skills Predict Peer Relationship Quality among Secondary School Students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State (n = 645)

Model	R	R Square	Adj. R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Remarks
1	.677	.458	.442	11.98711	Moderate Extent

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Table 1 shows that interpersonal skills have a strong positive relationship with peer relationship quality, with an R value of 0.677. The R-squared value of 0.458 indicates that interpersonal skills account for 45.8% of the variation in peer relationship quality among the students. The adjusted R-squared of 0.442 confirms the model is fairly reliable, while the standard error (11.98711) shows a moderate level of prediction accuracy. Hence, interpersonal skills predict peer relationship quality to a moderate extent among secondary school students.

Table 2: Simple Regression Coefficient on the Extent to Which Empathy Predicts Peer Relationship Quality among Secondary School Students in Uyo Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State (n = 645)

Model	R	R Square	Adj. R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Remarks
1	.698	.487	.451	11.92224	Moderate Extent

Table 2 shows that empathy has a strong positive relationship with peer relationship quality, with an R value of 0.698. The R-squared value of 0.487 indicates that empathy accounts for 48.7% of the variation in peer relationship quality among the students. The adjusted R-squared of 0.451 confirms the model is fairly reliable, while the standard error (11.92224) shows a moderate level of prediction accuracy. Hence, empathy predicts peer relationship quality to a moderate extent among secondary school students.

Table 3: Simple regression coefficient on the extent to which social awareness predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State (n = 645)

Model	R	R Square	Adj. R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Remarks
1	.859	.737	.735	11.95466	High Extent

Table 3 shows that social awareness has a very strong positive relationship with peer relationship quality, with an R value of 0.859. The R-squared value of 0.737 indicates that social awareness accounts for 73.7% of the variation in peer

relationship quality among the students. The adjusted R-squared of 0.735 confirms the model is highly reliable, while the standard error (11.95466) indicates a good level of prediction accuracy. Hence, social awareness predicts peer relationship quality to a high extent among secondary school students.

Table 4: Summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which interpersonal skills predict peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State (n = 645)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19867.33	1	19867.33	004.43	.001
Residual	61319.67	643	78.20		
Total	81187.39	644			

Table 4 shows the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which interpersonal skills predict peer relationship quality among secondary school students. The result reveals an F-value of 204.43 with a significance value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05.

Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that interpersonal skills do not significantly predict peer relationship quality is rejected. This implies that interpersonal skills significantly predict peer relationship quality among secondary school students.

Table 5: Summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which empathy predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State (n = 645).

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	18832.55	1	18832.55	108.17	.001
Residual	62354.84	643	95.37		
Total	81187.39	644			

Table 5 shows the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which empathy predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students. The result reveals an F-value of 108.17 with a significance value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that empathy does not significantly

predict peer relationship quality is rejected. This implies that empathy significantly predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students.

Table 6: Summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which social awareness predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State (n = 645).

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	18651.06	1	18651.06	212.11	.000
Residual	62536.33	643	95.37		
Total	81187.39	644			

Table 6 shows the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which social awareness predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students. The result reveals an F-value of 212.11 with a significance value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that social awareness does not significantly predict peer relationship quality is rejected. This implies that social awareness significantly predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of data on the extent to which interpersonal skills predict peer relationship quality among secondary school students revealed that interpersonal skills contribute moderately to peer relationship quality. In addition, the test of the corresponding null hypothesis showed that interpersonal skills significantly predict peer relationship quality among secondary school students. This suggests that the ability of students to communicate effectively, cooperate, and relate well with others plays an important role in building and maintaining positive peer relationships. Interpersonal skills enable students to interact confidently, express their thoughts clearly, and engage in meaningful social exchanges within the school environment. Students who possess strong interpersonal skills are more likely to form friendships, resolve conflicts amicably, and experience social acceptance among their peers. This present finding is consistent with the study of Adebayo and Salami (2021), who found that interpersonal competence significantly enhances

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students' ability to build and sustain meaningful relationships. However, this finding contrasts with the work of Ogunleye and Adeyinka (2020), who reported that interpersonal skills alone may not significantly predict peer relationship quality, as other social and environmental factors may exert greater influence.

The analysis of data on the extent to which empathy predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students revealed that empathy contributes moderately to peer relationship quality. Furthermore, the test of the corresponding null hypothesis showed that empathy significantly predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students. This implies that students' ability to understand and share the feelings of others plays an important role in fostering positive relationships. Empathy enables students to show care, offer support, and avoid behaviors that may harm others, thereby promoting trust and emotional connection among peers. Students, who are empathetic, are more likely to engage in prosocial behaviors such as helping, sharing, and cooperating, which strengthen peer bonds and reduce conflicts. This present finding is in agreement with the study of Okeke and Eze (2019), who found that empathy significantly promotes positive peer interactions and relationship development among adolescents. However, this finding differs from the study of Nwachukwu and Obi (2022), who reported that empathy does not independently predict peer relationship quality when other factors such as communication patterns and personality traits are considered.

The analysis of data on the extent to which social awareness predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students revealed that social awareness contributes to a high extent to peer relationship quality. In addition, the test of the corresponding null hypothesis showed that social awareness significantly predicts peer relationship quality among secondary school students. The implication is that students' ability to understand social cues, interpret others' behaviors, and respond appropriately in social situations plays a major role in determining the quality of their peer relationships. Social awareness enables students to behave appropriately in different social contexts, avoid misunderstandings, and maintain positive interactions with their peers. Students who are socially aware are more likely to be accepted within peer groups, build trust, and sustain harmonious relationships. This present finding is consistent with

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the study of Adewale and Yusuf (2021), who found that social awareness significantly enhances students' social competence and interpersonal relationships. However, this finding contrasts with the work of Ibrahim and Musa (2023), who reported that social awareness alone may not fully determine peer relationship quality, as factors such as school climate and peer influence may also play significant roles.

Conclusion

In view of the findings, it was concluded that social skills are critical determinants of the quality of peer relationships among students. Students who possess higher levels of interpersonal skills, empathy, and especially social awareness are more likely to develop and maintain positive, supportive, and harmonious relationships with their peers.

Implications for Counseling

The findings of this study have important implications for counseling practice in secondary schools. Since social skills, especially social awareness, were found to significantly predict peer relationship quality, school counselors need to give greater attention to the development of these skills among students. This implies that counselors should make deliberate efforts to help students become more socially aware so they can better understand social cues, interpret the feelings and behavior of others correctly, and respond appropriately in different social situations.

Furthermore, counseling services should focus on helping students develop empathy, effective communication, and conflict resolution skills, since these are essential for maintaining healthy peer relationships. When students learn how to understand the feelings of others, express themselves clearly, and handle disagreements peacefully, they are more likely to enjoy positive and harmonious interactions with their peers. This makes counseling an important tool for promoting peaceful coexistence and social adjustment within the school environment.

In addition, the study implies that group counseling should be encouraged in schools because it provides students with opportunities to interact, share

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experiences, and learn cooperative behaviors. Through group counseling sessions, students can develop mutual understanding, strengthen peer bonds, and learn how to work together in a supportive and respectful manner. This can go a long way in reducing cases of isolation, bullying, and unhealthy peer relationships.

Finally, the study highlights the importance of collaboration between counselors, teachers, and parents in reinforcing positive social behaviors among students. Since students' social development takes place both in school and at home, counselors cannot work effectively in isolation. A cooperative effort among these stakeholders will ensure that students receive consistent guidance, support, and encouragement needed to develop appropriate social skills and maintain quality peer relationships.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Secondary school authorities in the Uyo Local Government Area should incorporate social skills training programs into the school system to enhance students' interpersonal skills, empathy, and social awareness.
- ii. Guidance counselors in secondary schools in the study area should organize periodic seminars, workshops, and group activities aimed at improving students' social competence and peer relationship quality.
- iii. Secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area should adopt classroom strategies that encourage teamwork, cooperation, and positive peer interaction among students.

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SOCIAL SKILLS AND PEER RELATIONSHIP QUALITY QUESTIONNAIRE (SSPRQQ)

Instruction: Choose your response from the number of alternatives by ticking appropriately in the box provided.

Keys: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Section A: Social Skills

S/N	Interpersonal Skills	SA	A	D	SD
1	I find it easy to start conversations with my classmates.				
2	I express my ideas clearly when interacting with others.				
3	I listen attentively when my classmates are speaking.				
4	I find it easy to make new friends in school.				
5	I can maintain friendships for a long time.				
6	I respect the opinions of my classmates even when they differ from mine.				
	Empathy				
7	I understand how my classmates feel when they are upset.				
8	I show concern when a friend is going through a difficult time.				
9	I try to help my classmates when they are in need.				
10	I feel sad when I see someone being treated unfairly.				
11	I avoid doing things that may hurt others.				
12	I am sensitive to the feelings of my classmates.				
	Social Awareness				
13	I can easily understand how others feel from their facial expressions.				
14	I adjust my behaviour according to different social situations.				
15	I know when to speak and when to remain silent in a group.				
16	I behave appropriately in different school settings.				
17	I understand the rules guiding social interactions in school.				
18	I can tell when my actions may affect others negatively.				

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Section B: Peer Relationship Quality

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	I have good relationships with most of my classmates.				
2	My classmates accept me the way I am.				
3	I feel a sense of belonging among my classmates.				
4	I enjoy spending time with my classmates in school.				
5	My classmates treat me with respect.				
6	I feel comfortable sharing my ideas with my classmates.				
7	I have friends I can rely on in school.				
8	I feel valued by my classmates.				
9	I cooperate well with my classmates during group work.				
10	I can easily resolve misunderstandings with my friends.				
11	My classmates listen to me when I speak.				
12	I am satisfied with my friendships in school.				
13	My classmates appreciate my contributions in group activities.				
14	I feel confident when interacting with my classmates.				
15	I experience mutual understanding with my classmates.				